

Not so toxic: Antarctic *Pseudo-nitzschia* isolates give domoic acid the cold shoulder

The genus *Pseudo-nitzschia* is monitored worldwide because it can produce toxins, such as domoic acid (DA), which cause amnesic shellfish poisoning (ASP) in humans when accumulated in sea food [1]. Additionally, *Pseudo-nitzschia* species are associated with numerous large-scale harmful algal bloom (HAB) events that have led to mortality in marine organisms [2-3]. Approximately 27 species in this genus are known to potentially produce the neurotoxin DA along with up to six DA isomers (DA-IA, DA-IB, DA-IC, DA-ID, DA-IE and epi-DA) [4,5 and references therein]. These toxins can bioaccumulate in various organisms across different levels of the food web, including krill, bivalves, and fish, and have been detected in marine mammals and seabirds [4 and references therein]. Exposure to DA can result in seizures, reduced fitness, acute or chronic poisoning, and even death, particularly in marine mammals [3]. In humans, symptoms of ASP from DA exposure range from gastrointestinal, neurological, and cardiovascular to death in severe cases ([1]; Fig. 1).

Despite global monitoring efforts, Antarctica has not been a primary focus for studies on the occurrence and toxicity of the *Pseudo-nitzschia* genus. Several species have been detected in Antarctic waters, including the endemic *P. prolongatoides*, *P. subcurvata*, and *P. turgiduloides* [6-8]. Most Antarctic *Pseudo-nitzschia* strains tested for DA have shown no evidence of toxin production [7-8]; however, DA and the DA-IC isomer were detected in three *P. subcurvata* isolates from the Southern Ocean [9]. There is growing interest in HAB species detected in Antarctica, driven by the potential impacts of climate change on microalgal communities [9,10]. Investigating the presence of DA-producing *Pseudo-nitzschia* in this region is critical for understanding whether DA could impact the Antarctic food web and ecosystem dynamics.

Here we report the detection of *Pseudo-nitzschia* species at multiple sites in the Ross Sea Region, and over multiple years at Cape Evans (McMur-

do Sound, Antarctica). Environmental DNA (eDNA) metabarcoding targeting the 18S ribosomal DNA (rDNA) V9 region was employed to identify these species in seawater samples. Additionally, domoic acid and its isomers were screened in 17 *Pseudo-nitzschia* cultures isolated from Cape Evans in 2021, using liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) for quantification.

Methods and Materials

Samples for eDNA analyses were collected across multiple years (Fig. 2) via plankton net tows (15–20 µm mesh),

sea ice, and platelet ice cores (Fig. 3). Lower-latitude samples from Cape Adare to Coulman Island were gathered as part of the 2023 National Institute of Water and Atmospheric Research (NIWA) RV *Tangaroa* voyage. Additional samples were collected across various science seasons as part of on-continent field deployments through the Antarctic Science Platform and Antarctica New Zealand (Projects K892 and K043).

Samples for eDNA metabarcoding were preserved in RNAlater, ethanol, or 10% glycerol and stored at -80 °C until DNA extraction. These different preservation solutions were used due to the opportunistic re-use of samples from multiple projects spanning several Antarctic field seasons. From this point, all samples were processed, sequenced, and analysed following the protocol in Stuart et al. [11]. Although the 18S

Fig. 1. Symptoms and signs of Amnesic Shellfish Poisoning (ASP) caused by domoic acid (DA) toxicity in humans and DA toxicity symptoms in marine organisms. Information collated from [1-4].

Fig. 2. Details of sampling sites used in this study from the Ross Sea Region, Antarctica.

Fig. 3. Sampling for eDNA and live mixed samples in Antarctica, including (A) sea ice auger to collect brine samples, (B) plankton net deployed below ice, (C) SIPRE core drill for sea ice core samples and (D) sub-ice platelet layer (SIPL) sampler. Image credits: Jacqui Stuart.

rDNA V9 gene region is not the most common or effective marker for *Pseudo-nitzschia* species identification [12], it was chosen for a broader assessment of coastal marine microalgal communities (Stuart et al., submitted). The data presented here is a subset of that broader community assessment. Amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) identified as *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. by the PR2 database were further confirmed via BLAST (Basic Local Alignment Search Tool) at the National centre for Biotechnology Information (NCBI). The data analysis pipeline is available on GitHub <https://github.com/JustJaxz/AntarcticPseudos>. Phylogenetic reconstruction of ASVs was complete using Geneious Prime 2019.0.4 (<https://www.geneious.com>).

Microalgal cultures were isolated from unpreserved samples collected at Cape Evans in 2021, with cells isolated between December 2021 and January 2022 (Fig. 2). Cultures of *P. cf. subcurvata*, *P. subcurvata*, and *P. turgiduloides* were maintained at the Cawthron Institute Culture Collection of Microalgae (CICCM, Nelson, New Zealand) at 4 ± 1 °C and $80 \pm 10 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ photon irradiance (12:12 h L:D photoperiod) in f/2:K (1:1) media [20]. Species-level identification of the cultures was confirmed via Sanger sequencing of the ITS region (Table 1) following protocols previously described [5]. For LC-MS/MS analysis, cultures were transferred

to fresh f2 medium, harvested after 17 days of growth, and replicate cell counts were performed. Isolates were harvested in the early stationary growth phase by centrifugation (50 min, $3180 \times g$), and the resulting pellets were stored at -20 °C until further extraction.

Toxin extractions were completed using the protocol previously described [5]. Quantitative analysis of the culture extracts was conducted on a Waters Xevo TQ-S triple quadrupole mass spectrometer coupled with a Waters Acquity UPLC i-Class, equipped with a flow-through needle sample manager.

Results

Across all sites and years, two unique ASVs identified as *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. were detected via eDNA metabarcoding. ASVs identified as *Pseudo-nitzschia subcurvata* (ASV1) were detected at 12 of the 15 sites sampled within McMurdo Sound, with ASV abundance ranging between 226 – 16,597 (<1 – 33% of total eukaryotic microalgae ASVs) at individual sites (Fig. 4a). ASVs identi-

fied as *P. subcurvata* were detected for four of the five years sampling occurred at Cape Evans, showing the highest ASV abundance in 2010 and the lowest in 2022 (Figure 4b). ASVs identified as *Pseudo-nitzschia seriata* (ASV2) were only detected at site RI1, with an ASV abundance of 72.

Phylogenetic reconstruction of the ASVs resolved ASV1 with moderate support in a clade with *P. subcurvata* (Fig. 4c). ASV2 did not resolve within a specific clade but was identified via NCBI BLAST as *P. seriata* (BLAST results: Query cover: 100%; E-value: $3e-62$; % identity: 100%). No ASVs identified as *P. turgiduloides* were detected; however, only a single partial 18S sequence is available on GenBank for this species (Accession no. AY257839). The region overlap between the reference sequence and the ASVs from this study was only 68%, making reliable identification unlikely. No DA or its isomers were detected in any of the 17 cultures of *P. cf. subcurvata*, *P. subcurvata* and *P. turgiduloides* isolated from Cape Evans. All levels were below the limit of detection (Table 2).

Discussion

The detection of *Pseudo-nitzschia subcurvata* at multiple sites over several years in McMurdo Sound demonstrates the presence and persistence of this diatom species in Antarctic waters. This finding contributes to the growing evidence that HAB species, such as those belonging to *Pseudo-nitzschia*, are not limited to temperate or tropical regions [4, 14, 21]. Our results highlight that Antarctic waters, particularly in the Ross Sea Region, are home to potentially harmful microalgal species. This aligns with studies identifying HAB species in other areas around Antarctica, including the Antarctic Peninsula [17], Southern Ocean [16] and Weddell Sea [15].

Metabarcoding analysis revealed that *P. subcurvata* was prevalent across multiple years at the Cape Evans site,

Table 1. Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (BLAST) results of representative *Pseudo-nitzschia* sp. isolates from Cape Evans.

Strain code	GenBank accession number	Gene	BLAST match	Percent identity	Coverage	E-value
CAWB176	PQ276752	Internal transcribed spacer region	<i>P. cf. subcurvata</i>	99.58%	100%	0
CAWB179	PQ276753		<i>P. subcurvata</i>	100%	100%	0
CAWB178	PQ276754		<i>P. turgiduloides</i>	99.86%	100%	0

Fig. 4. Amplicon sequence variant (ASV) abundance identified as *Pseudo-nitzschia subcurvata* (ASV1) detected in samples from (A) sites in the Ross Sea Region. Sampling sites include Cape Adare (CA), Dugdale Glacier (DG), Possession Island (PI), Tucker Glacier (TG), Coulman Island (CI), Campbell Glacier (CG), Granite Harbour (GH), Cape Evans (CE), Array Site K043 (RI3), Turina Circle (RI4), New Ice K892 (RI1), SIMs Site (RI7), Old Ice K892 (RI2), K892 camp 2021 (RI6), K892 camp 2022 (RI5). (B) Abundance of *P. subcurvata* (ASV1) over time at Cape Evans, McMurdo Sound (CE); and (C) Maximum likelihood phylogenetic tree of detected *Pseudo-nitzschia* 18S ribosomal DNA V9 ASVs. Bootstrap support values are reported on the nodes. Evolutionary analyses were conducted using 10,000 bootstrap replications. The scale bar represents the number of substitutions per site.

Table 2. Summary of domoic acid (DA) and DA isomer production of 17 *Pseudo-nitzschia* isolates from Cape Evans, Antarctica, including species name, isolate or Cawthron Institute Culture Collection of Microalgae (CICCM) identifier and ranges of DA and isomers A-E. Zero values indicate that no toxins were detected at the limit of detection (LoD)

Species	Isolate or CICCM ID	Range of DA and DA Isomers Cell Quota ($\mu\text{g cell}^{-1}$)						
		DA	epi-DA	Iso-DA A	Iso-DA B	Iso-DA C	Iso-DA D	Iso-DA E
<i>P. cf. subcurvata</i>	K1Ps01	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>P. cf. subcurvata</i>	CAWB176	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>P. cf. subcurvata</i>	CAWB177	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>P. cf. subcurvata</i>	K1Ps06	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>P. cf. subcurvata</i>	K2Ps04	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>P. cf. subcurvata</i>	L4Ps01	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>P. cf. subcurvata</i>	L4Ps03	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>P. cf. subcurvata</i>	L4Ps04	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>P. turgiduloides</i>	CAWB178	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>P. turgiduloides</i>	K2Ps01	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>P. turgiduloides</i>	K2Ps02	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>P. turgiduloides</i>	K2Ps03	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>P. turgiduloides</i>	CAWB181	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>P. subcurvata</i>	K3Ps01	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>P. subcurvata</i>	CAWB179	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>P. subcurvata</i>	CAWB180	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>P. subcurvata</i>	L2Ps03	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

but no *P. turgiduloides* was detected, despite multiple isolates being established from samples at this location. This may be due to the limited availability of 18S rDNA V9 reference sequences for this species in both GenBank and the PR2 database. *P. seriata* was detected at one of the 15 sites, a species not previously reported in Antarctic waters. BLAST results had high coverage and confidence in the species identification; however, the length of the amplicon and the specificity of the selected gene region may limit accurate species-level assignment. This could also be due to the limited availability of reference sequences for Antarctic *Pseudo-nitzschia* species.

The lack of DA, epi-DA, or DA isomers A-E in our results is consistent with previous research indicating that most Antarctic *Pseudo-nitzschia* strains assessed do not show evidence of toxin production [7–8]. However, this contrasts with studies reporting DA production in some isolates of *P. subcurvata* from the Southern Ocean [9]. The 18S rDNA V9 region is not the most effective region for species-level identification of *Pseudo-nitzschia* but can provide valuable insights into the broader eukaryotic microalgal community [11]. It is important to note that other gene regions, such as the Internal Transcribed Spacer (ITS) regions, are more commonly used for precise species identification in phylogenetic studies of *Pseudo-nitzschia* [e.g. 5]. This limitation should be considered when interpreting our results, as the 18S rDNA V9 region may not provide the same level of taxonomic resolution as other markers, potentially underestimating the diversity of *Pseudo-nitzschia* species present in Antarctica.

This study highlights the presence of *P. subcurvata* in the Ross Sea Region of Antarctica and contributes to the growing understanding of the distribution of HAB species in polar ecosystems. Although no DA was detected in the cultured isolates, ongoing monitoring and research are essential to assess the potential risks posed by *Pseudo-nitzschia* in Antarctica. Future studies should consider using additional gene regions for more accurate species identification and include broader geographic and temporal sampling to better understand the potential impacts of HAB species on the food web in McMurdo Sound.

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References

1. Jeffery B et al 2004. *Food Chem Toxicol* 42: 545–557
2. Work TM et al 1993. *J Zoo Wildl Med* 24: 54–62
3. Lefebvre KA et al 2016. *Harmful Algae* 55: 13–24
4. Bates SS et al 2018. *Harmful Algae* 79: 3–43
5. Nishimura T et al 2021. *Toxins* 13: 637
6. Almandoz GO et al 2007. *Polar Biology* 31: 429–442
7. Silver MW et al 2010. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 107: 20762–20767
8. Ferrario ME & S Lincea. 2006. *Nova Hedwigia Beiheft* 130: 1
9. Olesen AJ et al 2021. *Toxins* 13: 93
10. Liu C et al 2022. *Polar Biology* 45: 1495–1512
11. Stuart J et al 2024. *Scientific Reports* 14: 64422
12. Quijano-Scheggia SI et al 2020. *PLoS One* 15: e0231902.

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First report of *Ostreopsis cf. siamensis* exceeding alert thresholds in Bay of Plentzia (South-East Bay of Biscay)

Fig. 1. Location of the sampling site.

Several species of benthic dinoflagellates belonging to the genus *Ostreopsis* are potentially toxic and were originally distributed mostly in warm and tropical

waters. Their presence has been associated with several toxic episodes affecting humans, with symptoms including dermatological and respiratory issues

[1]. Palytoxin analogues, including ova-toxins, ostreocins and liguriatoxins, have been proposed as the toxins responsible for these health issues, although no direct evidence has yet been established [2, 3].

Since *Ostreopsis* was first reported in the Basque Country in 2007 [4], there has been a notable increase in its abundance and distribution along the Basque coast, and it is now common during the summer months [5, 6]. Notably, during summer 2021, *Ostreopsis* cell densities exceeded the alert threshold for the first time in the Bay of Biscay, resulting in the closure of several beaches. Chomérat *et al.* [7] determined that the blooms observed in the French Basque coast during summer 2021 were not monospecific, containing both *Ostreopsis cf. siamensis* and *Ostreopsis cf. ovata*, with the latter confirmed as the toxin producer. Concurrently, high densities of *Ostreopsis* spp. were also observed in San Sebastián on the Spanish Basque coast, where respiratory problems were reported among sunbathers. This